

Copper(II) Complexes of Morpholino Methyl Urea and Morpholino Methyl Thiourea

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Copper(II) complexes of morpholino methyl urea and morpholino methyl thiourea have been prepared and characterized by elemental analysis, electrical conductance and infrared and electronic spectral and magnetic measurements. It has been found that both the ligands are bidentate in these complexes.

METAL complexes of a number of N-alkyl and N-aryl substituted ureas¹⁻⁵ and thioureas⁶⁻¹¹ have been studied. In most of the cases reported, coordination of the substituted urea was through the carbonyl oxygen and that of the thiourea was through the thiocarbonyl sulphur atom. In a few cases however, nitrogen coordination was noticed¹²⁻¹⁵. Paul *et al* indicated the coordination of tetramethyl urea through its nitrogen to antimony¹². Coordination of urea through nitrogen to Pt(II) and Pd(II) has been suggested by Curran *et al*¹³. Though thioureas appear generally to complex to metals through sulphur, it is nitrogen coordinated¹⁴ in $TiCl_4(tu)_2$ (tu =thiourea). N,N-Dimethyl thiourea is also found to coordinate through nitrogen to Cu(I) and Pd(II) metal salts⁹. It is interesting to note that thiourea formed two different complexes with CdI_2 , one colourless and the other yellow. The ir data of $CdI_2 \cdot 2L$ (L =thiourea) indicated that in the colourless species, the coordination site was nitrogen while in the yellow compound the coordination was via sulphur¹⁵. The present paper reports on the preparation and characterization of a number of copper(II) complexes of two organic ligands, morpholino methyl urea (MMU) (I) and morpholino methyl thiourea (MMTU) (II).

Survey of literature showed no previous report of any metal complexes of MMU and MMTU. The ligands MMU and MMTU have in each five possible coordination sites. It is of interest to determine which of these sites are actually involved in complexation with the metal ion.

Experimental

MMU¹⁶ was prepared by the reaction of ice-cooled aqueous formaldehyde with urea and mor-

pholine. After standing for 10 hr at room temp., the solution was concentrated and cooled. The solid formed was suction filtered, air-dried and recrystallised from ethanol. MMTU was prepared and purified in the same manner using thiourea in the place of urea. Copper(II) chloride, bromide, nitrate, perchlorate and sulphate complexes were prepared by adding a solution of the metal salt in a non-aqueous solvent (ethanol, *n*-butanol, dimethylformamide, etc.) to a solution of the ligand (MMU or MMTU) in the same solvent in a 1:2 mole ratio and then refluxing for about 2 hr on a water bath. The solid complexes were filtered, washed with hot ethanol and ether and finally vacuum dried. Complexes of $CuSO_4$ were prepared in dimethylformamide and the complexes of $Cu(NO_3)_2$ in ethanol while those of $CuCl_2$, $CuBr_2$ and $Cu(ClO_4)_2$ were prepared in *n*-butanol. Attempts to prepare pure MMTU complex of $CuBr_2$ were not successful and also the composition of MMU complex of $CuBr_2$ was different from those of other complexes.

Conductance was measured in 10^{-3} M dimethylformamide solutions using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin Elmer 597 IR spectrophotometer as KBr discs. The electronic spectra of a few complexes as acetone solutions were recorded on a Carl-Zeiss DMR 21 UV-visible double beam recording spectrophotometer provided with quartz cells. The spectra for the remaining complexes could not be recorded because of their insolubility in common organic solvents. Magnetic susceptibilities of the solids were measured on a Gouy balance at room temp. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen contents of the ligands and the complexes were determined using micro analytical methods. Copper, halides and sulphate were analysed using standard procedures¹⁷. Nitrate and perchlorate were not separately estimated. Elaborate care was taken to ensure that water was absent from the complexes.

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TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA AND OTHER PROPERTIES OF THE LIGANDS AND THEIR COMPLEXES

Compound	Colour	Analysis % , Found/(Calcd.)					μ_{eff} (903K) B.M.	$\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mole}^{-1}$ ($10^{-3} M$ in DMF)
		Copper	Anion	Carbon	Hydrogen	Nitrogen		
MMU	Colourless	—	—	45.32 (45.28)	8.19 (8.18)	26.44 (26.42)	—	—
CuCl ₂ .MMU	Brownish yellow	22.2 (21.65)	24.00 (24.19)	24.01 (24.54)	4.34 (4.43)	14.01 (14.31)	2.20	38.0
CuBr ₂ .4MMU	Green	7.22 (7.39)	18.54 (18.61)	38.60 (38.51)	6.07 (6.05)	19.60 (19.55)	1.83	11.3
Cu(NO ₃) ₂ .MMU	Bluish green	19.03 (18.34)	— (35.79)	20.85 (20.78)	3.82 (3.75)	20.96 (20.20)	1.87	20.3
Cu(ClO ₄) ₂ .2MMU	Green	11.26 (10.95)	— (34.29)	25.00 (24.81)	4.51 (4.48)	14.58 (14.47)	1.88	68.0
CuSO ₄ .MMU	Green	19.05 (19.95)	31.00 (30.84)	22.55 (22.60)	4.07 (4.08)	13.15 (13.18)	0.97	10.5
MMTU	Colourless	—	—	41.20 (41.14)	7.44 (7.43)	24.03 (24.00)	—	—
CuCl ₂ .MMTU	Brown	20.00 (20.53)	22.52 (22.94)	22.94 (23.27)	4.14 (4.20)	13.98 (13.57)	1.93	11.2
Cu(NO ₃) ₂ .MMTU	Dark green	17.92 (17.34)	— (33.83)	19.80 (19.86)	3.59 (3.58)	19.95 (19.31)	1.83	18.2
Cu(ClO ₄) ₂ .2MMTU	Brown	10.21 (10.37)	— (32.48)	24.05 (23.51)	4.34 (4.25)	14.03 (13.72)	1.88	74.0
CuSO ₄ .MMTU	Yellowish green	18.42 (19.00)	28.03 (28.71)	21.46 (21.52)	3.88 (3.89)	12.52 (12.55)	0.90	9.6

Results and Discussion

From chemical analysis (Table 1) of the MMU complexes, it is found that they have the compositions $\text{CuX}_n\cdot\text{MMU}$ ($n = 2$ or 1 ; $X = \text{Cl}, \text{NO}_3, \text{SO}_4$), $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2\cdot 2\text{MMU}$ and $\text{CuBr}_2\cdot 4\text{MMU}$. Complexes of MMTU are also found to have similar stoichiometries, $\text{CuX}_n\cdot\text{MMTU}$ ($n = 2$ or 1 ; $X = \text{Cl}, \text{NO}_3, \text{SO}_4$) and $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2\cdot 2\text{MMTU}$. The range of molar conductance¹⁸ of $10^{-3}M$ solutions of the complexes in DMF suggests that all of them are non-electrolytes, indicating that the anions of the copper(II) salts are also involved in coordination.³ The coordination of some of the anions is also inferred from ir spectra. Magnetic moments and colours of the complexes are presented in Table 1. $\text{CuCl}_2\cdot\text{MMU}$ exhibits an absorption peak at 13.8 kK and has a room temp. magnetic moment value of 2.20 B. M. Based on maximum absorption and magnetic moment, it is suggested that copper(II) is constrained in a square planar arrangement. A chloro complex of copper(II) ion having absorption maximum at about 14.0 kK had been assigned a constrained square planar configuration¹⁹. $\text{CuBr}_2\cdot 4\text{MMU}$ shows absorption at 17.8 kK which is typical of a distorted octahedral configuration for copper(II)²⁰. The magnetic moment value (1.83 B.M.) of $\text{CuBr}_2\cdot 4\text{MMU}$ is also in support of distorted octahedral symmetry for copper(II). As the diffuse reflectance spectra of the insoluble complexes could not be recorded, their tentative configurations were assigned on the basis of magnetic data. Magnetic moment values obtained for $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2\cdot\text{MMU}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2\cdot 2\text{MMU}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2\cdot\text{MMTU}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2\cdot 2\text{MMTU}$ support distorted octahedral configurations for these complexes and from the value for $\text{CuCl}_2\cdot\text{MMTU}$ a constrained square planar configuration as that of $\text{CuCl}_2\cdot\text{MMU}$

is suggested. But the sub-normal magnetic moment values of $\text{CuSO}_4\cdot\text{MMU}$ and $\text{CuSO}_4\cdot\text{MMTU}$ may perhaps be due to metal-metal interactions as suggested elsewhere¹¹.

IR spectra :

The important ir assignments are shown in Table 2. The assignments of ir bands of substituted ureas and substituted thioureas and their metal complexes have been fairly well established. When the thiourea ligand is coordinated to the metal through sulphur mainly (C-S) vibrational modes absorbing at about 1300 and 710-770 cm^{-1} should either be lowered or split or both⁶. Similarly, if the urea ligand coordinates through the carbonyl oxygen, (C=O) stretching mode at about 1650 cm^{-1} should be lowered or split. This important infrared spectral criterion of lowering or splitting of absorption frequencies of C-Z (Z=O or S) vibrational modes of ureas or thioureas due to complexation with a metal ion through oxygen/sulphur of ureas/thioureas has also been supported by X-ray diffraction crystallographic studies²¹⁻²⁴. Similar negative shifts should occur in the (N-H) vibrational modes if coordination takes place through amide nitrogen of MMU or MMTU. However, this criterion is complicated by varying degrees of hydrogen bonding likely to occur in ureas and thioureas and their metal complexes. In the case of MMU and MMTU complexes, if coordination was also to occur through morpholine ring nitrogen or oxygen there should be a shift in absorption due to ring (C-N-C) or (C-O-C) vibrational modes.

In all the MMTU complexes studied there is a clear lowering by about 30 cm^{-1} of the ligand band at about 1300 cm^{-1} and very much lowering of the band at about 770 cm^{-1} , indicating metal-sulphur

TABLE 2—IMPORTANT IR BANDS (in cm^{-1}) OF THE LIGANDS AND THEIR COMPLEXES

Compound	N-H stretch		N-H bend and O-N stretch		Mainly C=Z and O-N stretch		Morpholine ring (C-N-O) stretch		Morpholine ring (O-O-O) stretch	
	MMU	MMTU	MMU	MMTU	MMU C=O	MMTU O=S	MMU	MMTU	MMU	MMTU
MMU	3425 s 3380 s	—	1565 s 1445 m 1840 s	—	1650 s	—	1165 s 1150 s	—	1105 s	—
MMTU	—	3370 s 3390 m 3175 s	—	1640 s 1525 s 1455 m	—	1295 s 770 ms	—	1165 m 1135 m	—	1100 s
$\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot \text{L}$	3450 br 3200 m	3250 br 3150 br	1440 s 1880 m 1820 m	1820 s 1540 m 1410 m	1630 br	1230 w 680-670 s	1110 s 1080 s	1115-1080 m	1110 s 1080 s	1100 m
$\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{L}$	3540 s 3350 s	3350 m 3250 m 3150 m	1550 w 1420 s 1940 s	1620 s 1545 m 1830 s	1630 s	1280 w 600-500 br	1140 w 1120 w	1145 w 1090 w	1110 1080	1100 m
$\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{L}$	3420 m 3320 m	3370 br	1560 w 1540 w 1445 w	1610 m 1540 w 1520 w	1645-1635 m	1250-1230 w 670-610 m	1140 br 1080 s	1110-1090 m	1100 m	1100 m
$\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot \text{L}$	3550 m	3250 s	1550 sh 1480 m 1380 m	1605 s 1540 w 1440 w	1620-1590 s	1300-1280 w 600 br,s	1100 br,s 1090 br,s	1090 br,s	1100 br,s	1100 br,s
$\text{CuBr}_2 \cdot 4\text{MMU}$	3450 s	—	1560 w 1540 w 1445 w	—	1640 1630 s	—	1190 w 1080 w	—	1110 w	—

s = strong, m = medium, ms = medium strong, br = broad, sh = shoulder, L = MMU/MMTU, Z = O/S

bonding. In the case of MMU complexes the carbonyl stretching mode of free MMU at 1650 cm^{-1} is lowered by about 20 cm^{-1} due to metal-oxygen bonding.

The metal seems to prefer to coordinate through the carbonyl oxygen atom in MMU and sulphur atom in MMTU possibly because of the higher electron densities prevailing on these atoms than on the amide nitrogen atoms due to the different resonating structures^{2,5} (III, IV and V). In this connec-

(Z = O or S; R = -OH, NC₄H₉, O)

tion it may be mentioned that the copper(II) ion has not unambiguously exhibited "Class A" properties in its complex chemistry^{2,6}. In addition, the morpholine ring (C-N-C) stretching modes of free MMU at $1165-1150 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and that of free MMTU at $1165-1135 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are found to be lowered or split due to bonding of ring nitrogen to the metal centre. There have also been earlier reports^{4,7} suggesting coordination through ring nitrogen in ligands of similar size. Both MMU and MMTU act as bidentate chelating ligands here leading to the formation of a six membered ring structure of considerable stability as shown below. But in $\text{CuBr}_2 \cdot 4\text{MMU}$, the ligand coordinates through carbonyl oxygen only as is evidenced from its ir spectrum.

It was established from the vapour phase electron diffraction study^{2,7} that free morpholine is having

(VI)

(Z = O or S; M = Cu)

the chair conformation. So it is likely that the morpholine ring is present in the chair form in MMU and MMTU also. Further, morpholine ring in the less symmetric boat form is expected to give rise to more number of bands in the ir when compared to those in the chair form. Since the broad features of the ir spectra of the ligands and their complexes recorded in our work appear to be the same, it is suggested that the conformation of the morpholine ring in the complexes is not different from that in the free ligands.

A close examination of the ir spectra of the MMTU complexes revealed the lowering of (N-H) stretching frequencies, whereas in MMU complexes the lowering of (N-H) stretching frequencies was not noticed. This may be perhaps due to less pronounced hydrogen bonding interactions in the solid MMU complexes than in pure MMU solid and more pronounced hydrogen bonding interactions in the solid MMTU complexes than in pure MMTU solid.

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